

Phase transition in potassium hydrogen phthalate crystals –effect of various molar concentration of L-Proline

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Abstract:

This paper Investigate the crystalline nature of potassium hydrogen phthalate by adding L-Proline in three different molar concentrations. The crystals prepared by the slow evaporation method and characterized by Ultraviolet spectrum, Fourier Transform of Infrared analysis and Powder x-ray diffraction techniques. We observed all these materials are good absorption and transmission in UV region. As we calculated the energy that there is a loss of energy due to the inelastic scattering occurs in UV analysis. The Phase transition takes place as we increased the concentration of L-Proline with potassium hydrogen phthalate. For first and third molar concentration, the samples crystalized in orthorhombic system, and for fifth molar concentration the crystals crystallized in monoclinic system. But the crystals have Cmc21, Ibca and C121 space groups for first molar, third molar and fifth molar concentration respectively. Caglioti parameters, particle size, systematic absences were also analysed by powder peak pattern of this crystals. The Size and Strain graph plot of Williamson-Hall plot and crystallite size distribution graph of Warren-Aver Bach method interprets strain coefficient, size coefficient and L graph of $(\Delta d/d)\%$ versus length of peaks pattern predicted by PXRD data.

Keywords: UV-Vis, FT-IR, PXRD, Williamson-Hall Plot, Warren-Aver Bach Method.

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